

1+MG Incidental Findings Policy - Background and References

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Susanne Rebers and Adrian Thorogood on behalf of B1MG WP2

Contact: adrian.thorogood@uni.lu

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Background

This background document supports the 1+MG Incidental Findings Policy - Summary and Recommendations.

The task described in the grant proposal was to develop recommendations for minimal standards for 1+MG on how to deal with incidental findings (IFs). The recommendations are based on a review of current best practices and guidelines, summarized below.

Methods

The review included guidelines addressing IFs in both research and healthcare contexts. Existing policies were reviewed and interpreted for application in a large-scale pan-European genomic data sharing initiative.

WP2 of B1MG has developed and maintains a living [inventory](#) of existing guidelines relevant for the ethical and legal governance of a data sharing initiative. The guidelines in the inventory were reviewed to identify recommendations concerning the handling of IFs. The inventory includes guidelines, policies, recommendations, including those published in academic journals. We extended research beyond the inventory by also reviewing relevant ELSI literature. In terms of legal aspects relating to IFs, this background relies on a legal taxonomy of different national legislations developed as part of WP2. This research was also informed by discussion in healthcare and research use case workshops, which addressed questions of the types of potential IFs that could emerge through secondary use for research and healthcare purposes, and expectations of how they should be handled.

The territorial scope of the guidelines focused on the European context. However, we also included some important guidelines from international bodies and other jurisdictions, including the United States and Canada. Our focus on the European context is justified by the fact that differences in health care systems, societal norms and legal regulations have important implications for policies of IFs, leading to potential divergence between Europe and non-European countries. For example, it is more common in the US than in Europe to search for secondary findings or to return variants of unknown significance to sequenced individuals.

Categories of genomic findings of individual health relevance

Genomic findings of individual health relevance may be categorized in different ways, including the following definitions relevant to be used in a large European data-sharing initiative:

- **Incidental Findings (IFs)** - a finding concerning an individual research participant or patient that has health [or reproductive] importance for the individual or his/her relatives. This term is sometimes used specifically for findings discovered in the course of research or healthcare, which are beyond the study or clinical aims.
- **Individual Research Results (IRRs)** - a finding concerning an individual research participant that has potential health [or reproductive] importance for the individual or his/her relatives and is discovered in the course of research in relation to the study aims.
- **Secondary Findings (SFs)** - a finding that is not the primary target of a test, but is an additional result deliberately analysed by the practitioner, usually based on a recommended list developed by an expert body or by a consensus of practitioners.
- **Genomic Test Re-interpretation** - where a patient receives a test result (e.g. genetic diagnosis) as part of his or her primary healthcare workup, the test result may change over time in a clinically relevant way, for example because of advances in general knowledge about the medical significance of genetic variants.

The discussion below explores the circumstances under which there is an ethical and/or legal obligation to report these findings to data subjects, out of respect for their welfare.

Legal considerations

There is a concern that a failure to return an IF could breach a healthcare professional's legal duties towards a patient. A failure to return might lead to liability under the theory of negligence or civil responsibility. Healthcare professionals have fiduciary duties towards patients; whether or not their legal duties extended to seeking for or reporting IFs would be determined according to the prevailing standard of care. Health researchers primarily aim to generate generalizable knowledge, though they have a duty of care towards participants.

Another theoretical basis for a legal duty to report IFs in genomic research or medicine is the duty to warn (common law) or the duty to rescue individuals in imminent danger (civil law). In the case of family members, this duty may be in tension with obligations of confidentiality towards the sequenced individual. Under Spain's biomedical research law, researchers have an obligation to return information to the participant's relatives to avoid serious harm, even where this conflicts with the participant's preferences.

More generally, European human rights documents highlight a "right to know" information of health relevance, potentially underpinning an obligation to report IFs (e.g., European Commission, *European Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine*,

1997). These documents also recognize a competing right not to know, which is also enshrined in a number of national laws (Thorogood et al., 2019), including Estonia's biobank law, Latvia's genomic research law, Italy's genetic data privacy law, and Germany's diagnostic act (clinical contexts only). This right not to know is typically implemented by seeking consent or offering an opt-out to receive incidental findings. The right may be overridden by a competing legal duty to inform, e.g., where there is a risk of serious harm, such as in the example of the Spanish law above.

Sequencing in research context

The guidelines below were written for biobanks and/or research databases that were meant to serve multiple research projects. None of the guidelines specifically cover the 1+MG situation in which data are collected and stored in several countries (or EU member states), all with different national legislations.

Developing an incidental findings policy

Before the start of a research project, an IFs policy should be set up. Such a policy, which can be part of the study protocol, should include for instance whether IFs are returned, and how (ISBER 2012, Aarts et al. 2017, Bovenberg et al. 2009, Lewis et al. 2021). The *Guide to the detection, management and communication of incidental findings for biobanks in BBMRI-NL* provides an extensive overview of how to set up an IFs policy and what considerations should be taken into account (Aarts et al. 2017). It is recommended that such a policy is discussed and approved by a research ethics committee (NIH, ISBER 2012, Bovenberg et al. 2009), and that the reporting preferences of the most important stakeholders are taken into account (Bovenberg et al. 2009). The Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH), *2021 Policy on Clinically Actionable Genomic Research Results* echoes these recommendations, additionally highlighting that the policy be revisited periodically, and that researchers should be held to account by other stakeholders for compliance with the policy (GA4GH, 2021, Lewis et al. 2021).

The policy should also indicate how IFs should be returned to research participants or their families. It is recommended that the IF is communicated promptly by a physician or researcher who understands the IF and its possible clinical significance, and who has good communication skills (Aarts et al. 2017). Importantly, the communication should not be handled by an external researcher who has received access to samples or data (Bovenberg et al. 2009). But before any return can take place, the finding should be discussed with clinical experts. Main topics of discussion should be what the clinical significance of the finding is, and whether feedback is warranted. If an IF was not anticipated beforehand (see below on how it is determined which findings should be

communicated), a multidisciplinary team should discuss the finding (Aarts et al. 2017). The policy should also contain emergency procedures to inform both participants and non-participants (Bovenberg et al. 2009).

The policy should describe several procedural aspects that should be dealt with before the start of the study, including:

- Setting up a committee or multidisciplinary team in case IFs occur that were not anticipated (Aarts et al. 2017, Bovenberg et al. 2009);
- Making arrangements with experts and/or laboratories for consultation and/or follow-up tests to confirm IFs (Aarts et al. 2017). If necessary, tests should be repeated under good laboratory practices by a certified diagnostic lab (NIH, Aarts et al. 2017);
- Instructing researchers and other relevant personnel on the protocol to follow when IFs are detected (Aarts et al. 2017);
- Coordinating with clinical specialists for prompt follow-up when necessary (Aarts et al. 2017)

Further, any policy should be realistic and only spell out obligations that can actually be met (Bovenberg et al. 2009). This includes funding and appropriately trained personnel (GA4GH 2021, Lewis et al. 2021). It should take into account potential future findings that may be found due to technological or scientific advancements. It should also describe what the termination of the research study or biobank means for the handling of IFs (Bovenberg et al. 2009).

Patient/participant consent and information

Current guidelines strongly recommend that IFs policies should be reflected in the patient/participant information (NIH, WMA 2002, revision 2016, ISBER 2012, Aarts et al. 2017, Fellmann, Rial-Sebbag et al. 2020, Bovenberg et al. 2009). This includes circumstances under which IFs would and would not be disclosed to participants (NIH) or to family members (NIH), also after the participant or patient is deceased (Fellmann, Rial-Sebbag et al. 2020). It should include what types of IFs may be returned (NIH, Fellmann, Rial-Sebbag et al. 2020), when (NIH), and how (NIH, Aarts et al. 2017), and whether or not participation may lead to any benefits (Bovenberg et al. 2009). Patients or participants should be informed that IFs may be returned by secondary investigators if data are shared through a data repository (NIH).

NIH specifies several other items that are specific for genetic IFs that should be specified in the informed consent process. Many of these items should be seen in light of an IFs policy that has a low threshold for reporting:

- That the clinical significance of some results may be unknown;

- That the absence of a result does not equate with absent or reduced disease risk;
- That future research may change the clinical significance attributed to results at the time of the investigation;
- Whether the study team will be responsible for providing updates to participants regarding the significance of individual results;
- Whether return of results is dependent on the age of the participants and whether participants will be given the opportunity to provide consent for return of results when they reach the age of majority;
- The relevance to reproductive planning of any results that are to be returned (for men and women of reproductive age and for women known to be pregnant at the time of enrollment) (NIH).

The BBMRI-NL guidelines recommend giving research participants the option of opting out of receiving information about IFs. However, in situations when serious harm could be inflicted on the participant or their relatives, this opt-out might be overruled by the researcher, after consulting an expert (Aarts et al. 2017). Asking participants about their individual reporting preferences is also part of the recommendations by Bovenberg et al. (2009). If a participant indicated not wanting to know (certain) IFs, not including them in a specific research study could be considered (Bovenberg et al. 2009).

Which IFs should be returned?

None of the guidelines give a specific list of genetic variants that should always be disclosed. Some guidelines however, outline criteria or processes to guide decisions on whether or not an IF should be returned.

The guideline of BBMRI-NL gives the following recommendations on how to determine which of the potential IFs should be reported to research participants:

- Consult the literature, best practices and/or a multidisciplinary team;
- Draw up a list of anticipated IFs in consultation with a multidisciplinary team, and decide together whether these need to be reported;
- When deciding this, consider the following criteria:
 - Is there a real risk of a serious disorder?
 - Is there a realistic management option that can be offered? (Aarts et al. 2017).

Additionally, benefits to the data subject should be weighed against any disadvantages (Bovenberg et al. 2009). These guidelines are based on the Dutch practice to use a cautious approach to the return of IFs, in which only high risks of a serious disorder that

is uncertain to be incorporated in the donor's current treatment, and for which a realistic management option can be offered.

As a starting point, the guideline recommends to consult the literature, best practices and experts, including the list of variants that warrant return of results by the American College of Medical Geneticists (Dorschner, Amendola et al. 2013; Miller et al. 2021). The GA4GH Policy recommends researchers to let themselves be guided by current clinical standards of care and by community involvement (GA4GH 2021, Lewis et al. 2021). The list of IFs that should be returned should be checked and updated regularly (Aarts et al. 2017).

The US-based NIH offers a broader list of types of IFs that could be considered in setting up an IFs policy:

- Medically preventable conditions;
- Medically relevant results with unclear treatment implications;
- Results of uncertain significance;
- Results with clinical implications for the individual, but which may be useful for reproductive planning (e.g., carrier status);
- Adult-onset disorders to children or their parents (NIH).

Other guidelines are less specific about how to determine which IFs should be returned. However, in many cases they implicitly imply that IFs of a severe and high-risk nature should be returned, for instance when referring to '*serious and significant findings (either within the scope of the research project or outside of its scope) that have serious and significant health implications for the participant or their genetic relatives*' (ISBER 2012). Bovenberg et al. explicitly refer to returning IFs that relate to a serious health condition and where the possibility of an individual health benefit is realistic: '*The basic factors guiding disclosure and non-disclosure decisions should be: nature and size of the health risk, validity of the research finding, clinical utility for the participant, feasibility of feedback and integrity of the research and the meaning and 'non'-meaning of findings for different groups.*' (2009). Findings with high clinical importance should be reported to the data subject, even if that means overriding the wish of the data subject not to be informed. For other findings with potential health implications, data subjects may be informed that they can access relevant information if they want to (Bovenberg et al. 2009).

Most guidelines do not specify between findings that may be relevant for the data subject or that may have implications for family members. Bovenberg et al. (2009) indicate that in general, biobanks should only return IFs to data subjects. Where relevant, data subjects are then responsible to communicate the finding to family members for whom the finding might be of relevance. However, after a data subject has

deceased, and a finding of high clinical relevance has been found, reasonable efforts should be made by the biobank to return the finding to them.

Practical Considerations and Building an Evidence Base

The potential benefits, risks, and costs of feedback of IFs in research are not clearly understood. It is important to identify these, and to develop an evidence base over time in order to refine policy over time. There are a number of analytic challenges to identify an IF, including uncertainty and change with updated bioinformatics pipelines, re-interpretation based on the clinical presentation of the individual, and mosaicism requiring alternative DNA samples (Kochan et al., 2020).

There are challenges in participant contact, including non-responders, decedents, and situations where the result was already known by the participant (Kochan et al., 2020).

Another key challenge that remains poorly understood is the hand-off of the IF to the healthcare system.

Sequencing in health care context

In summary, the following recommendations can be seen as the best practice in Europe in dealing with IFs in the health care setting (Matthijs et al. 2016; Van El et al. 2013; Vears et al. 2018):

- A protocol/policy on how to deal with IFs in the health care setting should be set up and followed;
- Patients should be informed about this policy, including:
 - The chance of IFs
 - A question whether the patient wants IFs to be returned, either through an opt-in or opt-out procedure
- When a patient does not consent to the return of IFs, this should be respected. However, this 'right not to know' may sometimes be overridden by professional responsibilities for life-threatening IFs
- Genetic variants that are beyond the aim of the clinical question, but are indicative of a serious health problem for the person tested or close relatives, should be reported. When a genetic variant has no health implications for the person tested or their family, they should not be reported;
- When there is insufficient evidence of the pathogenicity of a genetic variant (VUS; Variants of Unknown/Uncertain Significance), this variant should not be reported;
- Clinicians should explain the potential crossover with research to patients

- The EuroGentest guidelines recommend laboratories to confirm IFs before informing patients (Matthijs et al. 2016).

Recontacting When Test Results Change Over Time

Recontacting is the Establishment of a new contact—initiated by either former patient or clinician – with former patients, seen in the past, discharged from care, and no longer in an ongoing relationship with the specific healthcare professional involved (Carrieri et al. 2019).

Most often, recontacting concerns a contact established to communicate a re-interpretation of a genetic variant that was interpreted in the past. Although such a situation does not cover the definition of IFs as defined above, since the re-interpretation usually concerns a finding within the aims of the previous analysis. However, the recommendations about recontacting might be informative for the discussion on IFs, because as in IFs, it is about findings that usually occur a certain period of time after the data were collected and after a patient is still under treatment of its treating physician. The ESHG recommends the following:

- If possible, recontact should take place for findings with clinical or established personal utility, even though currently there is no duty to do so (recommendation 1);
- The decision to recontact should be based on the best interests of the patient/family (recommendation 2);
- Recontacting should be sustainable for the health care system and its workforce (recommendation 3);
- The allocation of dedicated resources for activities on recontacting should be considered (recommendation 4);
- Recontacting should strive to be equitable for patients from all socioeconomic backgrounds and contexts (recommendation 5);
- There is a need for professional consensus about what constitutes good practice regarding consent for recontacting (recommendation 6);
- Recontacting should be a shared responsibility with patients (recommendation 7);
- Recontacting should be a shared responsibility with the genetic laboratories (recommendation 8);
- Data sharing should be promoted (recommendation 9);
- Other stakeholders should also share responsibility for recontacting (recommendation 10);
- Do the best you can with limited resources (recommendation 11);

- Each country should define its own organizational policy on the recontact process (recommendation 12);
- More research is needed to inform responsible recontacting processes (recommendation 13) (Carrieri et al. 2019).

There is discussion on whether laboratories should reanalyze data to generate new findings. Both the guidelines from EuroGentest and the ‘points to consider’ based on expert opinions indicate that there is no obligation for laboratories to routinely reanalyze data systematically for novel findings (Matthijs et al. 2016, Vears et al. 2018). The latter however, indicates that if a laboratory learns that a specific variant is reclassified, it is ‘good clinical practice’ to identify patients and inform their clinicians.

Considerations for Minors

The UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, 1989 highlights that children have the right to their interests being a primary consideration in all decisions concerning their well-being. They have the right to be heard and the right to the highest attainable standard of health. Whole genome sequencing in pediatric contexts raises a number of challenges in relation to these rights, which will be addressed in a complementary task of WP2. This section reviews issues specific to the handling of IFs in pediatric contexts, which a focus on ensuring policy supports the best interests of the child.

General questions of when and what IFs to report apply equally in pediatric contexts. One potential conflict that may arise is between the welfare of the child and the autonomy interests of the parent. Should feedback of IFs in pediatrics that are actionable (i.e., preventable or treatable) during childhood be mandatory, regardless of the wishes of the parents? Mandatory reporting of such IFs to parents is recommended by the Canadian College of Medical Genetics (CCMG) (Boycott et al, 2015).

Another tension arises between the child’s welfare in adulthood, and the child’s right to know or not to know about health information in adulthood. Should feedback of IFs about adult-onset conditions be restricted? Or should parents be given discretion over such findings? (Vears, 2021) This may depend on whether or not the findings are actionable or not during adulthood. Restricting return can preserve the child’s right to an open future, the right to decide whether or not to be tested once he or she reaches the age of majority. But the feedback may also have implications for the health of the child’s parents, which is tied to the child’s own best interests. There is a chance that the child does not have another opportunity to be sequenced or informed of an adult onset condition. Canada’s CCMG recommends not returning actionable, adult-onset IFs unless the parents’ request this, and the disclosure would be actionable for the parent or another family member. (Boycott et al, 2015) The US ACMG recommends a list of secondary findings be reported from clinical sequencing, regardless of the age of the patient, but suggests patients (or their parents may opt-out). However, there is also advocacy for mandatory reporting of serious, medically actionable, childhood-onset

findings. (ACMG, 2015) The US ASHG recommends in research contexts (?) that parents should generally be able to opt out of receiving IFs, "...in general, parents should be able to decline to receive secondary findings in advance of genetic testing." (Botkin et al. 2015) However, the ASHG recommends that reporting of serious, medically actionable, child onset IFs should be mandatory. The ESHG states that certain IFs should generally be reported. In pediatric contexts, "In case of testing minors, guidelines need to be established as to what unsolicited information should be disclosed to balance the autonomy and interests of the child and the parental rights and needs (not) to receive information that may be in the interest of their (future) family." (van El et al. 2013)

Other considerations relate to the involvement of the child in consent and feedback processes in an age-appropriate manner. Decisions about sequencing and IFs, and associated communications, should be made by the appropriate parent(s) or legal guardian, unless the patient has reached legal maturity. Consent/assent should inform the parent/child if IFs may or may not be returned and under what conditions. "the pre-test counselling session with parents is an opportunity for health professionals to explore parents' wishes and ensure they have a good understanding of the information and its implications for both the child and the broader family." (Vears, 2021) Choices may be offered where appropriate. Some recommended consent clauses include the following: medically actionable during childhood will be returned; parents may choose to receive (or not) IFs actionable during adulthood or for family members; non-actionable adult-onset will not be returned. (GA4GH, 2021) Reporting of findings should consider appropriate ways to communicate the information to the child, and involving the child in subsequent healthcare decisions (Vears, 2021).

Common Principles / Variation in Europe (Return of IFs)

From the above review, we can ascertain some general principles applicable for handling IFs in the European context:

- Beneficence: information with a high clinical relevance may be returned to the benefit of the data subject or his/her relatives. Yet, duties in research differ from those in health care, though these fields can be blurred.
- Importance of the Right not to Know in Europe and Purpose Limitation Principle under Data Protection. This is typically operationalized by requiring (separate) consent to feedback of individual genomic findings.
- High consent requirements (e.g., pre-test genetic counselling) before predictive genetic testing or carrier screening (generally excluding the return of these findings as IFs).
- Cautious approach in Europe to actively seeking out Secondary Findings in healthcare contexts (and by extension also research contexts), given uncertain and unproven benefit-risk balance of "opportunistic screening". (e.g., De Wert et al. 2020)

- Professional obligation (duty to warn/rescue) in some countries/contexts for reporting life-saving information to the patient.
- Cautious approach to return 'non-actionable' findings.
- Common legal or ethical obligation to return serious, analytically/clinically valid, and clinically actionable IRRs and IFs to sequenced individuals from research contexts.
- Importance of having a plan for handling, assessing, and communicating individual genomic findings.
- The decision to participate in research should be based on solidarity. This means that having more access to health information than those who do not participate should not be assumed when participating. This argument of equality is also used in for instance the conservative European approach towards opportunistic screening: opportunistic screening would lead to differential access to health information based on availability instead of needs.
- Balance between benefits to data subject and burden (resources) on infrastructure and healthcare systems (distributive justice).

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